

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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ABOUT THE OAEBU DATA TRUST EFFORT

Originating in 2015, the OAeBU Data Trust effort has brought over 100 individuals across five continents together to surface and address the issues that complicate the analysis and use of book usage metrics for decision-making and open access advocacy. To date, the project has documented the complex OAeBU data supply chain,² launched pilots of open-source infrastructure for a usage data trust, and facilitated workshops to understand the ways in which scholars and specific staff roles at libraries, publishers, and publishing platforms and services rely on OAeBU data. While these use cases were documented to inform data trust service development, the project team recognizes that they provide broader insights into the evolving analytics and linked-data demands across the scholarly communications ecosystem.

METHODOLOGY

This document evolved from the outputs of multiple virtual ideation sessions and workshops among peer stakeholder groups. These community-oriented feedback mechanisms were advertised via the OAeBU Data Trust effort's communities of practice. Co-Editors Drummond and Hawkins translated meeting and asynchronous ideation outputs into a preliminary use case document, which was shared back for public comment via the project's communities of practice and social media.³ Public comment was incorporated into this document, with notes offered by community members included at the end of each section. Within this document the staff roles at libraries that interact with usage data are identified as personas. Then, use cases are listed with descriptions of why usage data is important or how it is applied for a given use case. Specific questions or queries of usage data that surfaced in discussion are noted.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Book publishers, publishing platforms and services, and libraries all rely on book usage data to inform their operations. Across these industries, staff must address the burden of managing and curating usage data provisioned in COUNTER-compliant and non-compliant reports,

1 https://educopia.org/data_trust/ and <https://zenodo.org/communities/oaebu>

2 Clarke, Michael, & Ricci, Laura. (2021, April 9). OA Books Supply Chain Mapping Report. Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4681725>

3 The OAeBU project's processes for communities of practice development and use case development are published in Drummond, Christina (2020). "Engaging Stakeholder Networks to Support Global OA Monograph Usage Analytics," Collaborative Librarianship: Vol. 12 : Iss. 2 , Article 9. <https://digitalcommons.du.edu/collaborativelibrarianship/vol12/iss2/9>

APIs, dashboards, and spreadsheets. These institutions individually manage, compile, and link usage-data metrics, some of which are provisioned via dashboard services for users ranging from scholars, research offices and funding agencies, to editors, collections and acquisitions managers, and administrative decision makers.

While the term “usage data” is often used today to refer to web analytics reports that tally page visits and file downloads, the use cases herein document a near future where linked usage data analytics regularly inform book publishing and scholarly communications operations. Publishers and libraries expressed interest in using OAeBU data analytics to inform overall investment, strategy and fundraising in OA programs. They noted how data on the location and context of access to OA eBooks can inform book marketing and dissemination strategy, acquisitions and collections development, and scholars’ promotion and tenure. OAeBU data also surfaced as vital to supporting the promotion of OA publication among scholars and to illustrating institutional impact on the local and global stage. Linked contextual usage data can illustrate how OA books reach targeted audiences in classrooms, among scholars, within industry, and among policy-makers.

OAeBU data is poised to inform customer service relationships as publishers and libraries seek to appreciate service provider niches, evaluate book hosting and dissemination arrangements, and understand what is returned from their OA investments. Simultaneously, publishing platforms and services leverage usage data to inform the research, development, sales, and marketing of their own infrastructure.

Diverse models for OA book publisher, from university or library-based publishers to commercial publisher OA teams, surfaced many common functional needs of OAeBU data for publishers as shown in the graphic below. However, their structures resulted in unique needs tied to administrative and sales reporting, as is reflected in their individual use cases.

LIBRARY OPEN ACCESS EBOOK USAGE (OAEBU) DATA USE CASES

Libraries use OAeBU data to report the impacts and usage of OA books to authors and administrators at their institution. When leveraged for analytics, OAeBU data can support library collections development, strategic planning, and OA resource promotion, in addition to OA program strategy, budgeting, and fund development. Access to OAeBU data can inform book benchmarking and dissemination strategy for librarians. It can illuminate the global and local impacts of OA investments while clarifying how readers access OA books through varied discovery platforms. Library staff roles that may interact with OAeBU data go beyond a library's administrators to roles such as subject librarians (liaisons), collections assessment staff and collections development managers, electronic resources librarians, and research support staff. Library IT staff supporting e-resources and systems may be responsible for OAeBU data management, curation, and visualization.

Multiple challenges face libraries working with OAeBU data. Reader privacy protections make it difficult to know if unauthenticated eBook usage is related to affiliated patrons. Non-standardized approaches to processing data for chapters and compilations cloud the reporting of OAeBU. OAeBU data management, curation, and linking are complex and time intensive. In addition to compiling COUNTER and non-COUNTER compliant data from library management systems, publishers, and book dissemination or aggregation services, staff may be asked to link OAeBU data to other institutional research datasets. Such time-intensive activities require expertise in data analytics, bibliometrics, and book publishing metadata that may be beyond what's available to smaller libraries.

Dean, University Librarian

Scholarly Communication

Collections Development

Liaison Librarian

IT

Use Case 1.

Promote OA publishing opportunities

Personas

"Faculty data can inspire students to publish OA."

Why | How

- a. **Provide data to support OA evangelism and advocacy aimed at encouraging people to publish OA**
 - i. to show examples of audience reach and platform-specific access for
 1. prior OA publications by authors in similar field
 2. open educational resources.
 - ii. to support outreach to library patrons and constituents
 1. PhD students
 2. faculty
 3. state or provincial library programs
 4. alumni or public patrons
 - iii. to support fundraising

Use Case 2.

Support budget planning for OA resources and initiatives

Concerns exist over the potential for OA costs to cut into collections budgets. Context is very important.

Quarterly data can surface trends while annual data is important for reporting.

Personas

"If no one is using it, would funding be better allocated somewhere else?"

"Note: Multiple participants stated that in their institution's support for OA initiatives wasn't strictly tied to their own faculty, patron, or institutional usage but instead was linked to broader impacts and public good."

a. Articulate the value proposition for OA

- i. on campus
 1. as impacts on student outcomes
 2. as impacts on faculty outcomes
- ii. in the local community
 1. as impacts of regional access
 - a. by alumni
 - i. for degree programs
 - ii. for continuing education or professional certification programs
 - b. by businesses
 - c. by policy makers

b. Report OA usage by academic unit, college or school

- i. to support library budgeting conducted via a Responsibility Center Management model, i.e. *"When individual faculties set library budgets."*
- ii. to support cost-sharing among units

c. Understand OA investment as a percentage of the collections budget

d. Inform discussion of what merits OA budget investment

- i. by establishing the return on investment (ROI) for an OA initiative
 1. to support ongoing funding of OA initiative(s)
 2. to strategically add content
 3. to justify library staffing to support OA publishing and OA resource discovery
 4. to support communications regarding incremental OA publishing costs
 5. to articulate public good or broader impacts of OA publishing

e. Understand OAEBU across different websites, i.e. platforms, services, and publishers

- i. to inform discussion of which platforms to support, i.e. to evaluate paying for memberships or services
- ii. to understand the volume of faculty OA publishing
 1. generally, across platforms
 2. through a specific access point, hosting or aggregation platform for OA books
 3. to articulate the cost per use per platform or service
 - a. by authenticated institutional users (patrons)
 - b. within a local geographic region or city

Use Case 3.

Understand and support OA resource use within the institution / on campus

Personas

- a. **Provide eBook usage reporting to complement non-OA title reports**
 - i. by reporting aggregated usage by institution
 - ii. by reporting aggregated usage by author
 1. with overall cross-platform usage by author
 2. with chapter level reporting for compilations
 - iii. by reporting aggregated usage for a specific book
 - iv. by reporting aggregated usage for a specific chapter
- b. **Understand whether OA material is being referenced in class reading lists**

e.g. "Is an OA eBook being used on a learning management system like Canvas, TELUS, or Moodle?"
- c. **Provide usage data reports to campus units**
 - i. Faculty Senate: to illustrate breadth and absence of activity
 - ii. Academic Affairs: to establish levels of OA activity by discipline
 - iii. Graduate School: to establish levels of OA publishing activity
 1. among advising faculty
 2. among graduate students
 - iv. Research Office: to indicate the impacts of OA publications through discipline or domain storytelling
- d. **Support or train faculty and/or students on how to create their own OA impact reports**
 - i. by providing self-service OA usage reports
 - ii. by supporting workshops for faculty or students
- e. **Promote scholarship by local authors**
 - i. by illustrating local and regional impact
 1. of books
 2. of chapters
- f. **Support collaboration and/or contributions with university press**
- g. **Understand what elements were accessed**
 - i. by differentiating between usage of Abstract, Table of Contents, and/or full text

Use Case 4.

Inform collections development strategy

Personas

"Which titles are being used from which providers?"

a. Understand how library patrons use OA collections

- i. by tracking demand in a collection to determine new things to support (e.g. understand user needs)
 1. understand need for new acquisitions
 2. support analysis of emerging models of acquisitions
- ii. to inform what is catalogued.
e.g. "If some of your users are accessing eBooks through a given provider that is not included in your library's discovery systems, you will want to include that provider in your systems so that your other users can also discover eBooks that way."
- iii. to inform acquisitions
- iv. to inform expenditures

b. Inform decisions on who to pay for access, e.g. direct with publisher or via aggregator

- i. by evaluating OA content access overlaps and niches across vendors
- ii. by understanding access on specific platforms for content from a given press or publisher

c. Inform acquisition strategy with usage as evidence

- i. to identify items for purchase
- ii. to inform disciplinary collection development based on access patterns

Use Case 5.

Collect, aggregate, and prepare data for reporting

Personas

a. Gather usage data from multiple sources

b. Input usage data into library's own data warehouse or research management system

c. Create data visualizations

d. Set up APIs to display usage data on websites, in Tableau, or other in data compilations

e. Create usage data dashboards for campus audiences, e.g. Library, and Research office